

THE HISTORICAL SITUATION OF THE TEMURID PERIOD AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE LITERATURE OF MOVAROUNNAHR

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Abstract. *The article analyzes and discusses issues related to the political, social and cultural situation of Movarounnahr during the reign of the Temurides, the contribution of prominent representatives of the dynasty to the development of the social and cultural life of society, the process of the emergence and formation of the Temurid Renaissance, and in it the place of scientists and literature of Movarounnahr.*

Key words: *ulema, sarbadars, reforms, genre, artisans, Kuragon, aruz, qasida.*

INTRODUCTION

After the invasion of the Mongols and the massacres and robberies of the population (1220), in Movarounnahr, as in other occupied territories, public life was very slowly restored. The Arabic term "Movarounnahr" means "beyond the river" and refers to the land north of the Amu Darya. The Arab geographer Yakut Hamavi considered the country Turan under this name. The territory of Movarounnahr in the Middle Ages conditionally covered the lands between the rivers Amu and Sir, and in modern science, this term refers to the territories of the rule of the Karakhanids, Khorezmshahs, Chigatoys, Timurids and Shaybanids. The cultural layer of the population, such as scientists, writers, poets and artists, emigrated to nearby and foreign countries: Western Iran, Asia Minor, India, or were sent captive to Mongolia. The spheres of economy, culture, art and science are also were in decline. For almost a century and a half, Mongolian khans from the descendants of Chingiz's son Chigatoy (1127-1241) ruled here. Although the Mongols conquered the country politically and militarily, they were unable to subdue the people spiritually, because their lower culture compared to the population of the region did not allow this.

Gradually, the Mongols formed two tendencies in relation to the settled population, the first group of which sought to massacre and exterminate the population, and the second group, in order to effectively exploit the population, tried to restore the destroyed economy. The monetary reforms carried out by supporters of the second direction in the early 70s of the XIII century by the ruling merchant Masudbek, the son of one of the prominent representatives of this direction, Ahmad Yalavoch, and in 1321 by Kabakhon, were steps towards improving the country's monetary condition. The descendants of Genghis Khan, accustomed to resettlement and robbery, not only failed to build a livable city here and did not allow the restoration of cultural centers, but also destroyed educated people who came out of the people so that fear reigned among the population, and they could not raise their heads against the Mongols. With all this instilling fear and destruction of the people, the Mongols could not break the will of the people, on the contrary, they gradually adopted the religion of the local population - Islam, and adapted to its customs. When the people's patience ran out, popular

uprisings against them began in different regions. The discontent of the masses, the uprisings led by the Sarbadors in Samarkand in 1365, especially the activities of Amir Temur Kuragoni (1336-1405) played a big role in stopping the arbitrariness of the invaders.

In such a situation, the rulers of Shakhrisabz, Bukhara, Termiz, Badakhshan, Khojent and Shosh were constantly at war with each other in the devastated Movarunnahr. Mutinies and conspiracies, massacres and robberies of the population brought hardship and poverty to the people. In such a period of feudal internecine strife and conflicts, young Temur entered the political arena as a skilled commander and was able to overcome the tyranny of the Mongols in the future. His father, Amir Turgai [7, 7], was from the tribe of the Barlos, and his mother, Niginamokh [12, 121], was the daughter of the famous jurist Sadrushsharia of Bukhara. His life and activities are divided into two periods, and in the first period of his life (1360-1386) he worked together with local rulers, Turkish and Tajik nobility [2, 6] on the way to establishing the future centralized government of powerful Movarounnahr and independent of the Mongol khans, against the collapse of the country and he waged war against petty rulers. As liberation movements grew among the people, in 1361 the Mongol khans again attacked and sacked Movarunnahr to suppress it. 15-year-old Temur was appointed by them as governor in the Kesh region, and later, due to historical necessity, his political and military vigilance, fierce battles and victories, he won the reign in Movarounnahr (1370), although, according to tradition, the Mongol successor was the ruler of the country, but in practice, power was in the hands of Amir Temur. He made Samarkand the main center of his empire and completely liberated Movarunnahr from the hands of the Mongols, gaining a reputation as a great commander.

The second period of his life and political activity (1386-1402) is known as three-year, five-year and seven-year military campaigns, and it is also of world significance. He spent half of his 72-year-old life in the war, fought exactly a thousand times and won all of them [12, 17]. He united the disparate peoples of Central Asia, took upon himself the impossible work of Alexander the Great, and connected the East with the West. During this period of his activity, he conquered Iran, Iraq, Transcaucasia, Egypt, Azerbaijan, Northern India, in particular, having conquered the Golden Horde saved the Russian state, and having conquered the Ottoman Empire saved Europe from their invasion, [4, 176], his kingdom with the center in Samarkand became one of the most powerful states in the world. Today, along with the military art of Alexander the Great and Napoleon, the military academies of the world study the military qualities of Amir Temur.

As soon as Amir Temur came to power, he began the improvement and construction of the empire he had created throughout the territory. His main attention was drawn to the creation of a powerful united state in Moravaunnahr. On the basis of peace, he established a state system that covered the territory of 27 countries. In order to improve the economic, political and cultural life of the country, he took decisive measures [6, 139-140]. Among these scientists, according to the sources, were the best experts on the science of dreams and music.

According to Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi and Ruy Gonzalez de Clavijo [4, 165], he dealt with issues of culture, architecture, science, such as mathematics, geometry, composition, literature, poetry, history and music. Now merchants from Rome, Arab countries, Iran and India first came to the capital of the kingdom - Samarkand, and then went to Mongolia and China. So merchants and representatives of distant countries of Europe, Asia Minor, the Volga region, Russia, Siberia, and the Far East came here. He brought order, discipline and inviolability of the law to the country, raised the economy and culture, and established ties with foreign countries. Sahibkiran built roads and bridges, rivers and irrigation facilities [2, 18], caravanserais and baths, mosques and madrasahs [1, 4-10], in the territories under their control [11, 1174], according to Clavijo, especially in Samarkand, he laid 17 beautiful gardens that were not less than those of Paris [9, 17]. Movarunnahr became the most beautiful country in the East. Several favorable factors coincided with the fact that Temur made Samarkand, and not Shakhrisabz, the capital of his kingdom. In particular, its location in the center of Central Asia,

pleasant weather and rich natural resources were very suitable. Timur sought to turn Samarkand into the best city in the world, among other things, he built settlements around the city like the best Islamic cities, such as Baghdad, Damascus, Egypt, Shiraz, Sultania. Greek historians and chroniclers wrote about Samarkand, poets and writers wrote works, gazelles and odes, tourists and scientists from East and West were amazed to see in this center many great and important creations of folk masters, great builders who embodied the skill of people. Mirza Babur noted that the city had such gates as Furuza, Akhanin, Shaikhzoda, Gozuristan, Suzangaron and Chorrah, and the length of the city wall was 10,600 steps. During the period of Timur and the Timurids, Kuksaroy, a public mosque and Bibikhanum madrasah, several mausoleums and collections in Shakhi-Zinda, palaces and gardens throughout Samarkand with the names Bagi (garden) Chinar, Bagi Shamal, Bagi Dilkusho, Bagi Bikhisht, Bagi Nav were built in Samarkand. Roads were laid, bridges were built across Kukhak and Zarafshan, Amu Darya and Syr Darya, a canal was laid around Tashkent, and the city of Okhangaran was founded from Syr Darya to Okhangaran. In Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, Ferghana, Turkestan, irrigation facilities, caravanserais and other facilities were built. On a large scale, the construction of cities and villages, baths, madrasahs, mausoleums began. Many builders from the countries conquered by Timur, along with local craftsmen and architects and artisans, were involved in construction work.

In addition to his political and military abilities, Timur was a noble person, from an early age he learned to write and read, at the age of 7 he memorized the Quran, and under the influence of his maternal grandfather, the judge of Bukhara, Sadrush-Shariat Ubaydullah ibn Mahmud, he became interested in people of knowledge and virtues [11, 165], he mastered such modern sciences as medicine, mathematics, astronomy, architecture, history, studied the history of the Arab, Persian, Turkic peoples and their religious, secular and philosophical knowledge. Strengthening his state, along with relying on artisans, merchants, sheikhs and the religion of Islam, he created conditions for the development of science and natural science, literature and art, as well as the establishment of domestic and foreign trade. In each country he conquered, he sent to the central cities, especially to Samarkand, scientists and nobles, theologians, artists, representatives of literature and art, and also raised the art of architecture, painting and drawing to a high level [8, 5-30]. He established diplomatic, commercial and economic relations with the most famous foreign countries such as Byzantium, Venice, Genoa, France, Spain and England. Thanks to his activities in Central Asia, a solid foundation was laid for the Timur Renaissance. According to researchers of the history of Central Asian culture, during this period, especially in Samarkand, on the basis of the development of original art and the best artistic achievements of the peoples of the Middle and Near East, a completely new synthesized art arose. At the end of the 14th century, as a result of the fact that Movarounnahr became the main center of the creative forces of the Near and Middle East, a new trend appeared in art. Even historians of the same period openly acknowledged this innovation. For example, Ibn Arabshah gave information about the palaces around the city and said that they were built with a "new method". In particular, the search for new attractive means of architecture was expressed in polychronous decor, which acquired an unprecedented splendor throughout the East of the same period. In the field of painting of Central Asia of the XIV-XV centuries, there is a tendency to use, along with the traditional literary themes of the Middle Ages, modern themes, trends in different genres, improvement of painting skills, composition, etc. In the 15th century, a high level was reached by decorative and artistic crafts, the development of which organically went with architecture, engraving, and subject art. The dependence of various arts is manifested in wood and stone carving, carpet weaving, decoration of handwritten books, the best examples of ceramic and metal vessels. Artisans and masters of Samarkand not only played a big role in the economy of the city, but also actively participated in its cultural life and had a great influence on its development. Craftsmen constituted the cultural class of the cities of Central Asia. For example, famous poets, musicians and historians came from artisans and small traders. In particular, the poets from

Samarkand were Javhari - the head of the soap business, Mavlona Khavafi - a tailor, Mavlona Mir Argun - a tailor, Mavlona Kabuli - a rope seller, Mavlona Tolei - a tailor, Bisoti - a weaver.

The relationship of Amir Temur with the greatest poet of that period, Kamoli Khujandi, is also noteworthy. These two great figures of the era - one as an incomparable politician, and the other as a sweet-spoken poet - became the best examples of the relationship between teacher and student. In particular, their first meeting took place in an extraordinary way, and the sources of the period expressed this very vividly. For example, the famous poet of the literary circle of Herat Abdullahi Khatifi, who is the son of the sister of Maulana Abdurrahmani Jami, wrote about this event in his masnavi "Temurnoma" [12, 121]. According to it, on the orders of his father, young Temur sold some of his sheep in the market, and suddenly he met a dervish there, who had a letter with a quatrain in his hand, and he turned the crowd of people that he would sell it for a thousand dinars in gold. Temur, who knew the price of poetry and speech, bought it, came to his father and opened the letter. It was written in a quatrain that those who had previously conquered the world completely erased oppression and injustice in their time. There were Jamshid, Suleiman and Iskandar, now you get up and gird your belt, because now it's your turn, and the name of the poet is Kamoliddin Khujandi.

Although artisans produced original art products, according to the current laws, they occupied only 11th place among the 12 classes of the population. According to sources, Amir Temur, as a good religious scholar, knew the laws of Islam well. He was very interested in the science and culture of that period. He had great respect for people of science and culture. According to sources, when he attacked cities, he first sent a message to the scientists and artists to leave, and then attacked. Ali Yazdi says that once during the occupation of the city, one of the opponents of the city entered the house of one of the city's scientists and took refuge there. Thanks to the respect of the scientist, the whole family of the scientist, as well as the enemy, were spared [11, 993-994]. At the beginning of the 15th century, there was a weakness in the structure of Temur's statehood. Since he appointed his sons and grandsons as rulers in some parts of his empire, this led to conflicts and quarrels between the Temur princes for the throne. He had 4 sons and 2 daughters (Jahangir Mirza, Umarshaikh Mirza, Miron Shah Mirza, Shahrukh Mirza, Tagayshah Begum, Sultan Bakht Begum), together with his grandchildren he had 36 heirs [11, 1003] and divided the kingdom into 4, including Northern Iran (Dzhurjan and Mozandaran) and Sehiston with a center from Herat to Shahrukh; Western Iran, Iraq, Armenia and Azerbaijan, centered on Tabriz to Miron Shah; Southern Iran (Persia) with a center in Shiraz was given to Umarsheikh, the current territory of Afghanistan, Northern India with a center in Ghazna, and later Balkh was given to Pir Muhammad Suyurgal (reward) [5, 704].

Among these heirs, his grandson, Khalil Sultan, son of Miron Shah, شاه میران بن سلطان خلیل, had more chances to become crown prince, because he was a "good-natured, all-forgiving and elegant" [10, 267] young man, and he was also brave, prudent and smart in the military field. In addition to being the brave son of Miron Shah, he was married to the daughter of Amir Temur Sultanbegim's sister, Sherbeka, and all doors were open for him to become the owner of the throne, but he once got drunk at the wedding of Mirza Ulugbek (بزرگ طوی) [11, 462] and fell in love with a maid named Shadiya, and it went so far that he later secretly married her. Amir Temur after a forty-day wedding, on November 27, 1404, prepared an army with the aim of conquering China and moved to the city of Aksulot. There, he heard the news of Khalil Sultan's secret marriage to a concubine named Shadiya, who became pregnant by him, and ordered both of them to be quickly arrested and executed, but was spared by the intervention of Sarai Mul Khanum. He ordered Khalil Sultan to go to Tashkent to gather an army. In 1405, he reached the city of Utror, where his health deteriorated, and he called the leaders to him, declared his grandson Pir Muhammad son of Jahangir - Pir Muhammad bin Jahangir Mirza the crown prince, and bequeathed that everyone obey him unconditionally [6, 533- 534] and died on February 18. After his death, the empire he created fell apart, and Movarunnahr became the scene of a bloody dynastic struggle.

Most of the dignitaries and nobles in Samarkand did not know about this will, but the news quickly reached Sultan Khalil, who was in Tashkent, and he, with the encouragement of his entourage, moved towards Samarkand, freely entered the city, sat on the throne and declared himself emir (1405-1409). Later, as a result of the struggle for the throne, his political rivals Sultan Hussein and Pir Mohammed were killed. They reached an agreement with Shahrukh Mirza that he would rule independently in Herat and Khalil Sultan in Samarkand without interference from each other. But despite his successes, he could not hold power for a long time, as he made a number of political mistakes. Firstly, his wife Shadia directly interfered in the affairs of the state, and secondly, Khalil Sultan himself, who was a lover of poetry, held literary parties and gradually allowed negligence in the affairs of the state. In the third, he dismissed Amir Temur's proxies from their positions and appointed mainly relatives of his wife Shodiamulk [3, 192]. So, for 4 years of his reign, he plundered and destroyed the treasures collected by Amir Temur for 36 years [11, 997]. Meanwhile, Miron Shah was killed in one of the battles with the Karakuunly-Turkmen led by Karayusuf, and Azerbaijan and Iraq were taken out of the control of the Timurids. The same factors led to the rise of his opponents, and as a result of the attack of the Fergana governor Khudaidod and Sheikh Nuriddin, he was defeated, captured and imprisoned in Shahrukhiya. Upon learning of the defeat of Khalil Sultan, Shahrukh Mirza moved to Samarkand, and having captured him, released Khalil Sultan from prison and appointed him governor of the province of Ray, where he soon died. He transferred the administration of Samarkand to his son Muhammad Turgay Ulugbek Mirza (1409-1449) [7, 18]. As a result, under Shahrukh, the Timurid kingdom was practically divided into two states: Khorasan under his control with a center in Herat and Movarunnahr under the rule of Ulugbek in Samarkand.

With the help of his father Shahrukh, Ulugbek first conquered Khorezm (1413), then Fergana and Kashgar (1415), and in the 30-40s of the XV century he fought against Abulhair Khan on the Kypchak plain to protect the population from the invasion of nomads - pastoralists. His monetary reforms in 1428 also contributed to economic improvement. Despite achieving some success in the field of public administration, he focused his attention on science. In particular, he built a large observatory in Kuhak (1328) and, together with the largest representatives of science, compiled the astronomical work *Ziji Jadidi Kuragoni* (1437). Shahrukh was killed in 1447 during the suppression of a rebellion by his grandson Sultan Muhammad in the province of Ray, and the state of the empire became unstable. Finally, Mirza Ulugbek was killed at the age of 56 at the instigation of the opposition by order of his son Abdulatif.

After the death of Ulugbek, power passed into the hands of his nephew and son-in-law - the son of Ibrahim Sultan, the grandson of Shahrukh - Abdullah Mirza (1450-1451). Meanwhile, the grandson of Miron Shah, Abu Said, also fought for the throne. In a battle between them in 1451, Abdullah's army was defeated and he himself was killed. Power passed into the hands of Abu Said Mirza, that is, again to the descendants of Miron Shah. Abu Said managed to maintain relative peace and stability in the territory until 1469, and he was eventually defeated and died in a fierce battle to capture Tebrez from the Turkmen. With the death of Abu Said, the west of Khorasan and all of Iran separated from the Temurian Empire, while the west of Iran remained under the rule of the Akkuyunlu dynasty. After his death, his sons Sultan Ahmed Mirza (1469-1494), Sultan Mahmud and Sultan Ali ruled in Samarkand until 1500. The emerging kingdom of Timur was no longer a single centralized state. Taking advantage of this situation, the nomadic tribes of the Kipchak steppe, the Shaibanids, invaded Central Asia and laid siege to Samarkand. Babur Mirza (1483-1530), the last representative of the Timurids, was also forced to leave Samarkand because of the betrayal of his relatives and friends. After his occupation, the Shaybans completely subjugated the other provinces of Movarunnahr (1500) and Khorasan (1507).

Thus, for 137 years of their reign (1370-1407), the Timurids defeated the tyranny of the Mongols and contributed to the development of all spheres of life, including culture and literature, which led to the

formation of the Temurid Renaissance.

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